

On some implications of formalized theories in our life

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Abstract

The formalized theories in which are considered different types of logics give us an easier way of understanding of our own interpretations of the concepts and of the events of life.

In the paper "Paradoxist mathematics" [1] Smarandache proved that contradiction is not a catastrophe even in mathematics and he taught us how to handle it. Even more, this can encourage us in our life, for the infinite dimensional capacity of human condition. Through this paper we meditate on the great diversity of human condition seen through the axiomatization of a formalized theory. Thus the science gives some explanations for the life and the life inspires the science.

We denote $S:=(N,R,A)$ an axiomatical system of a formalized theory; N and R are fundamental notions and relations and A is a list of hypothesis propozitions (axioms in the modern meaning).

$$T(S):=<S,consecS>$$

$T(S)$ is the theory deduced from S and its consequences based on a logic L .

If the great Gauss said that the mathematicians were not prepared to accept the new Geometry of N. Lobacewski and J. Bolyai, today we can see

that the evolution of absolute Geometry [3] brings us a great number of non-euclidean Geometries.

This development and the great varieties of Geometries and Mathematics structures help us in some directions for the self-understanding.

Accordingly to the great illuminated ones we have a sublime inner structure, which could bring us more respect of each other and, also, the self-respect.

Well, then why are we so different? Certainly this depends of the degree in which these innate qualities are left to be manifested or are blocked. We can see different kinds of people who can distinguish each other after the degree of manifestation of their own qualities. This depends of the degree of the ignorance, or of the negligence or even of the denial of one or more of pure aspects of our inside, shortly this is correlated with our "Inner Geometry", a notion introduced by us in [2].

Our "Inner Geometry" can be different from a moment to another, from a person to another, and it depends of the self-knowledge, which is a subject which addresses to a seeker of truth with a scientific attitude and is a search since immemorial times. It is the knowledge of all civilizations and of the evolution and so we should treat it with much respect for our benefit.

Each one of us can see that sometimes we feel some of our qualities, but sometimes we substitute them in something opposite. In this way, we can see that our "Inner Geometry" represent an immense variety. Why?

There is an alive complete "instrument" put in our inside. This alive "hipercomputer" works by the manifestation of its powers, by the parasympathetic nervous system and by the right, left and central sympathetic nervous system. All we are doing in our evolution is expressed

by our nervous system. This is an alive, spontaneous and natural process. Our contribution is to leave it to manifest in its natural manner. Usually we disturb it by our: too much worries and irritations. When our pure energy is left to manifest, it connects us, our subtle being, to the Allpervading power of God's Love, of the primordial power who creates and does all alive work. The anterior state can be compared with that of a seed before to be put in the earth.

The Foundation of Geometry could help us to explain the great diversity of human beings. How? Thinking to the some aspects of our "Inner Geometry".

1. Have we, ever, put the questions about our "Inner Geometry"? If we had, we can ask ourselves about of the system $S=(N,R,A)$ which we accept in our existence. We can ask about the order of values in our life.

2. Even the consciousness of the importance of a foundation of our existence is differently understood or accepted, or is denied.

3. The way in which we develop $T(S)$, the degree of the knowledge of $T(S)$ at a given moment, and the logic L we use for $T(S)$ are arguments to a deeper understanding of the diversity of human condition.

4. If we make a choice of the system S , what kind of interpretations give we to the fundamental notions N and relations R ? What significance attribute we to the elements of N , R and A of S ? From here the great human variety.

5. Is it our existence one ful of wisdom, or is it one ful of contradictions and confusions?

Our problems could be naturally solved when in our "inner computer", our competent energy is working in our life. Then we live after natural laws. To imply to these aspects we would dare to stimulate, as a provocation, all

the scientists. We all are invited to pay attention for a better self-understanding and for a more harmonious integration in the life, by using our inner possibilities.

The Foundation of Mathematics invites us to a profound meditation about self-knowledge, to a consciousness of our inner riches and such to avoid to waste our own energies, which could affect our healthiness.

6. The acceptance of our inner possibilities do not suppose an inactivity state, but the actions with much respect and love for our neighbours and for self-respect. Such we assume the responsibility for our facts and this help us not to block some subtle centers of our inner being, of our subtle body and to pay attention to our own Logic *L*.

7. Is this possible in a world full of selfishness? We are even optimistic and encourage our readers for a reflection of what Foundation of a theory provoke us in a correlation with the self-knowledge and the awakening of our inner possibilities, about all illuminaries assure us, even if for the moment, our poor logic is vexed.

When we deny or we use not, one or some of our inner possibilities, our "Inner Geometry" is perturbed from its natural state.

The degradation of the life to which all assist is an explanation of the ignoring of our inner capacities.

In "Paradoxist Mathematics" in [1] the author says about its Anti-Geometries: "everything is considered not in a nihilistic way, but in a positive one". And we agree this. A possible positive way is that of understanding of the actual state of human condition. The new concepts in Mathematics given in [1] were written at a time when the author experienced a political totalitarianism system: "I wanted to be free in life -

hence I got the same feelings in science. It is a revolt against all petrified knowledge" [1].

To these we would add that we could, also, "revolt" in front of this decadence and degradation by considering our greatness about we were created and using it in a more and more wisdom life. How? Through some silent minutes: to be what we are, and so to permit to our subtle body to work after its own laws.

More we experience our nature, closer we are to be free and health. What is a plant without water, or without the light of sun?

When we begin to live our life as an expression of our universality, of our divinity, then we begin to give a correct answer to the question: "who really I am"? Realize I that my essence is a spiritual one? Let us realize this and let us identify with our own essence. This is our right, and this time has come. It is like the time to bloom flowers. We all potentially have so many availabilities of love, of serenity, of peace, of creativity. They are available. Let all consider them and identify with them. Then we enjoy of our inner innate qualities and the divine power, who is in all beings as consciousness as intelligence, as the power of reflection, of modesty, of peace, of compassion, of satisfaction and others, can work naturally. When we experience the power of the Self, we can see that the ego is not, who really I am. The ego is our self-image, it is our social mask, it is the role we are playing in society. But I am my pure essence. So, ego, is not my true identification.

Our true nature is complete free of fear, because it recognizes in every one else, the same pure nature and even in his errors can do the difference between what the essence is and what is not.

How to get our correct identification? A deep and pure desire that what is divine in us to manifest; all days not to forget to spend a time in the nature, and to have a short time at least, to simply Be, to realize that it is a responsibility to contribute to our own evolution with sincerity, making important steps to understand the laws of nature, based not on a blind faith, but on a real one, what can be verified.

Through all we mentioned in this paper we would like to do the Mathematics a force of life for our better understanding and a force which invite us to use more and more our inner life, which were not enough explored.

References

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